

Teaching Effectiveness on Pre-Service Teachers' Pedagogical Competence and Internship Performance: Basis for an Action Plan

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ABSTRACT

This study explored the relationship between teaching effectiveness, pedagogical competence, and internship performance among pre-service teachers at Buenavista Community College. A total of 288 graduating students from the BEED, BSED English, and BSED Mathematics programs participated. Utilizing a descriptive-correlational research design, data were gathered through adapted questionnaires and analyzed using mean, standard deviation, and Pearson correlation. Results showed that faculty were generally rated as "Effective," particularly in Commitment, with slightly lower ratings in Teaching for Independent Learning and

Management of Learning. Pre-service teachers were assessed by cooperating teachers as having "Proficient Competence," especially in Content Knowledge, Learning Environment, and Curriculum Planning. However, lower ratings in Personal Growth and Professional Development indicated a need for greater emphasis on reflective practices and professional readiness. Internship performance was largely positive, with over 72% of participants receiving Outstanding to Very Good ratings, validating the strength of the teacher education program. A minority of students received lower ratings, highlighting the need for targeted support such as mentoring and skill development. Correlation analysis revealed a weak and statistically insignificant relationship between teaching effectiveness and pedagogical competence, suggesting other influencing factors like student motivation. A significant but negative correlation was found between teaching effectiveness and internship performance, possibly reflecting a disconnect between academic and field evaluation criteria. A weak positive correlation between pedagogical competence and internship performance approached significance, emphasizing the complex nature of teacher readiness. Overall, the study underscores the need for a more integrated and evidence-based approach to teacher education that aligns instruction, competence development, and internship assessment.

Keywords: *Teaching Effectiveness, Pedagogical Competence, Internship Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The quality of future educators directly influences student learning outcomes and the overall educational system. Beyond knowledge transmission, effective instruction inspires, equips, and empowers future educators, significantly affecting their preparedness for professional challenges, including their performance in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET).

Competent teaching extends beyond skill acquisition—it serves as a motivator for pre-service teachers. A strong pedagogical foundation enhances their confidence, helping them approach learning tasks with a deeper appreciation for their future careers. This self-assurance fosters a more engaging and enriching classroom environment. Furthermore, it strengthens their ability to apply theoretical knowledge in high-stakes assessments like the LET, where mastery of pedagogical concepts is crucial.

On a global scale, Dervenis et al. (2022), as cited by Chen and Liu (2023), emphasize that teaching skills are fundamental to effective instruction at any level. Without these competencies, educators struggle to engage students and fulfill their professional responsibilities. Similarly, Agsalud (2017) underscores the importance of faculty teaching effectiveness in driving educational success at the national level. Locally, Bauzon (2001), as cited by Bulilan (2023), highlights that instructors' must possess adaptable skills to navigate the evolving educational landscape, reinforcing the necessity of faculty development.

This study also aligns with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 4, which advocates for quality, inclusive, and equitable education. Ensuring effective faculty instruction fosters pre-service teachers' foundational competencies.

While research has explored the significance of pedagogical competence in shaping pre-service teachers (Chetty et al., 2014; Burroughs et al., 2019; Sukarni et al., 2023), a key population gap remains: most studies focus on universities, leaving colleges largely unexamined. For example, Afalla & Fabelico (2020) examined pedagogical competence among pre-service teachers in a state university in the Cagayan Valley Region, Philippines, suggesting that faculty instruction plays a pivotal role in developing teaching skills. Similarly, Dacer (2024) studied pre-service teacher competencies at the Central Bicol State University of Agriculture, recommending continuous curriculum updates. Thus, the absence of direct studies linking the quality of instruction provided by faculty in teacher education programs to the competency of pre-service teachers at the college level underscores a significant population gap (Miles, 2017).

This study is anchored Article XIV, Section 1 and 2 of the Philippine Constitution which states that “the state shall protect and promote the right of all the citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all”. Moreover, “the state shall establish, maintain and support a complete, adequate and integrated system of education relevant to the needs of the people and society”. This provision presents a strong commitment to education as a fundamental right and a key driver of individual and societal progress. It outlines the government's responsibility to ensure

quality education is accessible to all and to create a comprehensive, relevant, and integrated system that meets the evolving needs of the Philippines

Along the same lines, Article III, Chapter 1 section 23: Objectives of Tertiary Education of Batas Pambansa Blg. 232, also known as “The Education Act of 1982, is an act providing for the establishment and maintenance of an integrated system of education in the Philippines” which states the objectives of a tertiary education; “to train the nation's manpower in the skills required for national development and to develop the professions that will provide leadership for the nation”. This provision presents a two-pronged approach to tertiary education in the Philippines, emphasizing both its role in developing skilled manpower and nurturing future leaders.

Moreover, as a framework of teacher quality, the Department of Education through the Teacher Education Council (TEC), issued DepEd Order no. 42, s. 2017 entitled National Adoption and Implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) supports this study. The adoption and implementation of the new Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers recognize the importance of professional standards in the continuing professional development and advancement of teachers based on the principle of lifelong learning which refers to the systematic acquisition, upgrade of knowledge, skills and attitude, and promotes self-directed learning. PPST originated from the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) which was revised to make it even more attuned to the changes brought about by numerous national and global frameworks and responsive to the changing needs of the 21st-century learners who are creative, critical thinkers, excited to collaborate and communicate in various platforms, savvy in information, technology, and media, and flexible (Gepila Jr. 2020 p.740).

Bandura's (1977) Self-Efficacy Theory asserts that individuals' belief in their capabilities significantly influences their motivation, effort, and perseverance when facing challenges. In the context of teacher education, this theory suggests that faculty members who demonstrate effective teaching practices and provide constructive feedback can foster higher self-efficacy among pre-service teachers. As these future educators observe skilled faculty, internalize positive reinforcement, and engage in guided practice, their confidence in their pedagogical abilities grows. This enhanced self-efficacy can translate into stronger classroom performance during internships. Supporting this idea, Sehgal et al. (2017), as cited by Hussain and Khan (2022), found that teacher effectiveness is closely tied to self-efficacy, collaboration, and leadership. Their findings emphasize the importance of cultivating environments where teachers—both experienced and pre-service—feel empowered through support systems that promote quality instruction, meaningful teacher-student interactions, and effective classroom management.

Complementing this perspective is Vygotsky's (1978) Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which focuses on the difference between what a learner can achieve independently and what they can achieve with the assistance of a more knowledgeable other (MKO), such as a mentor teacher or faculty member. In this study, ZPD underscores the importance of guided instruction and mentorship in helping pre-service teachers bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical classroom application. As cited by Poon and Chan (2023), researchers such as Denhere et al. (2013), He et al. (2023), and Tada

et al. (2023) emphasized that support from an MKO contributes to increased competence, self-efficacy, and resilience. This theory highlights the social dimension of learning, where meaningful interactions with mentors and peers play a crucial role in the development of pedagogical skills and professional confidence.

Lastly, the study draws on Constructivist Theory, primarily attributed to Piaget (1952) and further supported by Fosnot (2013) and Bruner (1996). This theory posits that learners actively construct knowledge through experience, reflection, and interaction. It challenges the traditional passive model of learning by emphasizing the importance of experiential, student-centered, and problem-based learning. For pre-service teachers, this means that pedagogical competence is not simply transmitted but actively built through teaching practice, feedback, collaboration, and reflective thinking. Constructivist strategies such as scaffolding and real-world application during internships allow pre-service teachers to internalize teaching concepts and refine their instructional skills in meaningful contexts.

The effectiveness of faculty teaching in teacher education programs plays a crucial role in shaping the pedagogical competence of pre-service teachers. Skilled faculty provide pre-service teachers with invaluable learning opportunities by modelling effective teaching strategies for instruction, assessment, and student engagement, serving as inspiring role models and shaping their development into competent educators.

Babu and Mendro, (2003) as cited by Francisco and Caingcoy (2022) on their study stated that teachers are the most powerful influence on student success. It highlights the significant power teachers hold in shaping student success. Their expertise, dedication, and personalized approach can have a profound impact on students' academic progress, social development, and overall well-being.

On similar grounds, Jacob et al., (2020) on their study claimed that teachers are the most important factor in students' learning. With the critical roles that teachers play in schools, their competencies in terms of knowledge and skills, need to be looked into for these are factors that affect learners' performance (Francisco & Caingcoy 2022 p. 546). Hence, it gives emphasis on the connection between teacher competencies and student performance. While recognizing the limitations of focusing solely on this aspect, it encourages efforts to ensure educators possess the necessary knowledge and skills to fulfil their critical roles and ultimately contribute to better learning outcomes for all students.

Furthermore, on the study of Panda (2019) as cited by Dumaguing and Yango (2023) affirmed that high-quality teachers are essential for the future growth of national educational systems and economic vitality. It highlights the strategic importance of investing in teachers as key players in national development. By fostering a pipeline of highly skilled and dedicated educators, nations can cultivate a well-equipped workforce, fuel economic growth, and create a prosperous future for all.

On top of that, Kporyi (2021) on his study, concluded that the pedagogical competence of teachers could help promote deep knowledge, understanding and expectation among students if teacher's pedagogical competencies are effective. Also, when teachers increase their knowledge and competence to

manage the classroom, they could provide high expectations for student's social support, guidance and independent thought in learning. The statement emphasizes the crucial role of teacher pedagogical competence in promoting deeper learning, high expectations, and independent thought among students.

Meanwhile, Seidel and Shavelson (2007) on their study as cited by Bardach and Klassen (2020) viewed high quality teaching as the dynamic and interactive process of creating, fostering, adapting, and negotiating learning environments in which all students are supported in activities that have a good chance of improving learning. This paints a comprehensive picture of high-quality teaching as a multi-faceted and ever-evolving process. By embracing this dynamic approach, teachers can create learning environments that truly enable all students to reach their full potential.

Thus, teaching effectiveness has a profound impact on student success in their chosen careers. Effective faculty equip students with the necessary knowledge, skills, and confidence, while nurturing their passion and resilience, ultimately preparing them to thrive in their future professional endeavors.

The future of education is not confined to the four walls of a classroom but rather rests on the shoulders of those who guide learning within them: our future educators. Equipping them with the necessary pedagogical skills isn't just about honing their abilities; it's about empowering them to shape the learning journeys of generations to come, a responsibility that demands investment and dedication.

Manigbas et al. (2024) on their study affirmed that pre-service teachers as future teachers should possess a high degree of competency to provide a conducive learning environment to accommodate the changing needs of the students. This implies the importance of equipping pre-service teachers with the necessary skills and knowledge to become effective educators who can foster positive learning experiences for all students, even as their needs and the educational landscape continue to evolve.

In like manner, on the study of Absolor (2023) he stated that future educators encounter numerous difficulties as a result of the complexity and breadth of education today. Therefore, it is essential for future teachers to be highly prepared and competent as they are the basis of just and efficient educational systems. The statement suggests that investing in the preparation and competence of teachers is crucial for creating a fair and effective education system that benefits all students. It acknowledges that well-equipped teachers are not just educators, but architects of a just and efficient learning environment for all.

Moreover, Sasmito and Wijaya (2022) emphasized that pedagogical competence is one of four competencies that should be possessed by a teacher. This underscores the vital role of pedagogical competence in equipping pre-service teachers with the necessary skills to become impactful educators and nurture future generations of learners.

Connected to the point above, Rahman (2014) on his study as cited by Sasmito and Wijaya (2022) stated that this competency is the teacher's ability to manage to learn includes planning, implementation and evaluation. This statement points out the multifaceted nature of "managing to learn" as a vital competency for pre-service teachers. By fostering this ability, they will be empowered to become lifelong learners, effective educators, and positive role models for their students.

Related to this, Greathouse et al. (2019); Mohamed et al. (2016); Giboney Wall, (2014) on their study as cited by Afalla and Fabelico (2022) stated that in student teaching, pre-service teachers need to refresh their learning in theory and subject courses, teaching methods, strategies and techniques and demonstrate the pedagogical material skills they gained from related courses prior to their teaching immersion. Hence, the importance of active learning and application of knowledge during student

teaching. By effectively refreshing their knowledge, implementing learned skills, and demonstrating their abilities, pre-service teachers gain valuable experience and confidence, preparing them to become successful and impactful educators.

On that note, the importance of pre-service teachers' pedagogical competence cannot be overstated. It sets the foundation for effective teaching, fostering positive learning environments, promoting student growth, and contributing to a more equitable and just society.

The transition from teacher-in-training to confident educator hinges on internship performance. This crucial phase bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and real-world practice, shaping pre-service teachers into effective changemakers in the classroom.

Laguador et al. (2020) on their study mentioned that internship is an important learning activity to practice what the students learned from theories. Thus, it highlights the value of experiential learning through internships, where students can translate theoretical knowledge into practical skills and gain valuable insights into their chosen field. This combination of learning and experience can be transformative and prepare students for a successful future.

In a similar note, Miller and Wilson (2010) cited by Reaves et al. (2023) student teaching internships provide opportunities for preservice teachers to develop skills in classroom instruction, student management, lesson preparation, personal and professional growth, and reflection as an educator. Hence, student teaching internships offer a powerful combination of real-world experience, skill development, and personal growth, preparing pre-service teachers for success in their future careers.

Damoco et al. (2023) on their study revealed that positive performance of the pre-service teachers highlights the effectiveness of the teaching internship in preparing them for their future careers. Their strong instructional-related skills, personal and social qualities, teacher qualities and motivation, and attitude towards punctuality and promptness demonstrate their readiness and competence as future teachers.

Moreover, In the study of Martin and Wikerson (2006) cited by Caraig (2018) they believed that students' internship experience enhanced their knowledge and skills. Therefore, internships are proving to be valuable learning experiences, boosting students' knowledge and skillsets.

Teachers have an important role in national development. With them, the country can produce and nurture learners who can lead the country to growth and advancement. Improving teacher quality and maintaining great teaching standards should therefore be accorded top priority for long-term and sustainable country building.

Sung et al. (2022) cited by Martin (2024) postulated that the Higher Education Institution (HEI) acknowledges the significance of professional standards in teachers' advancement and ongoing professional development to ensure the idea of lifelong learning. It is dedicated to helping educators and acknowledging the clear evidence that high-achieving students benefit greatly from having excellent teachers. Thus, the HEI believes that high-quality teachers are essential for successful education, and they support their faculty by setting standards, offering development opportunities, and fostering a culture of continuous learning. This creates a beneficial cycle where good teachers become even better, ultimately leading to improved student learning outcomes.

In a similar vein, Agsalud (2017) emphasized that faculty teaching effectiveness is crucial to student success. The study assessed commitment, subject knowledge, independent learning, and learning

management. Findings showed that faculty at Pangasinan State University–Asingan Campus are highly qualified, though few graduated with honors or attended national and international training. Hence, it is implied that PSU produced equally competent graduates as reflected by their competent educators.

In this study, the Faculty Evaluation Instrument (QCE of the NBC No.461) used by Agsalud (2017) was adopted to evaluate the faculty members' level of teaching effectiveness in terms of commitment, knowledge of the subject matter, teaching for independent learning and management of learning.

The cornerstone of any successful education system lies in its educators. Teachers' commitment plays a vital role in shaping student learning experiences, influencing academic achievement, and fostering a positive learning environment

Han et al. (2015) cited by Cansoy et al. (2020) on their study affirmed that teachers' commitment to school is related to their willingness to make efforts on behalf of the school reforms, which aim to develop the quality of instruction and improve collaboration among teachers at school, are directly related to teacher. Thus, it highlights the importance of considering teacher well-being, professional development, and collaborative strategies when implementing school reforms.

In addition, on the study of Sun (2015) cited by Cansoy et al. (2020) states that research related to teacher commitment has focused on teachers' commitment to teaching, students, school and change. Some studies have shown that teacher commitment is vital for following changes in instructional practices and for professional motivation.

To conclude, it underlines the invaluable role of teachers in shaping the future generations and emphasizes the need to invest in their well-being, professional development, and overall working conditions within an education system.

Teachers play a crucial role in shaping the minds of future generations. Their knowledge and understanding of the subject matter they teach are fundamental to effective instruction and student learning.

According to the study of Guerriero (2014) cited by Gamayao and Binas (2021) pedagogical content knowledge conceptualizes the ways of representing and formulating subject that makes comprehensible to others. Hence, PCK is the art of translation, transforming complex knowledge into a form that is meaningful and accessible for learners. This is a crucial skill for effective teaching and plays a vital role in fostering student engagement and understanding.

Meanwhile, on the study of Even (1993) cited by Gamayao and Binas (2021) stipulated that pedagogical content knowledge is also a unique form of knowledge for teaching which is based on subject matter knowledge, knowledge of potential student learning difficulties, and students' prior knowledge of specific concepts.

Moreover, Gamayao and Binas (2021) on their study revealed that teachers with outstanding pedagogical content knowledge combined with a high level of teaching competency build a strong foundation of education and producing highly competent and knowledgeable students. It also contributes to the well- organized learning environment, conducive learning for everyone, and thus provides effective learning.

All in all, it underscores the critical role of well-equipped teachers in shaping the future generations and emphasizes the importance of investing in their professional development to ensure they

possess both the subject matter expertise and the pedagogical skills necessary to deliver high-quality education.

In today's rapidly evolving world, equipping students with the ability to learn independently is crucial for their long-term success. This requires a shift in the traditional teacher-centered model towards a learner-centered approach, where teachers facilitate and guide students to become self-directed learners.

According to the study of Aminatun and Oktaviani (2019) they stated that teachers nowadays can use different medium to teach in every meeting they are teaching. Moreover, teachers are now demanded to make students become independent learners. Therefore, the roles of teachers are not only teaching, but also facilitate students to study.

To sum up, teachers now play a more facilitative role in empowering students to become independent learners who are actively engaged in their own learning journey. This shift requires teachers to be adaptable, innovative, and skilled in utilizing various resources to create meaningful and engaging learning experiences that foster both knowledge acquisition and critical thinking skills.

Education thrives on effective learning environments, and fostering such environments is the cornerstone of successful teaching. At the heart of this lies teachers' management of learning, a multifaceted process encompassing various strategies and practices.

Adham and Mahmudah (2021) on their study affirmed that one of the keys to the success of learning is good management. Research confirms that proper management of learning can create optimal learning conditions and neutralize the situation, particularly when there is a disturbance in the classroom during teaching and learning activities

In essence, good management fosters purposeful learning, allowing individuals to optimize their time, resources, and effort to achieve their desired learning outcomes.

The education landscape is constantly evolving, demanding teachers equipped with diverse pedagogical skills to foster effective learning in their students. However, evaluating and ensuring pre-service teachers possess these essential competencies remains a central challenge. This necessitates the development and implementation of robust standards to measure their pedagogical competence.

The Department of Education, through the Teacher Education Council (TEC), recognized the importance of professional development for teachers by issuing DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, which mandated the adoption and implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST). This move underscored the principle of lifelong learning, emphasizing the continuous acquisition and improvement of knowledge, skills, and attitudes.

The PPST evolved from the National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS) but was revised to better reflect the changing landscape of education. It is now designed to equip teachers with the capabilities needed to nurture 21st-century learners – individuals who are creative, critical thinkers, effective collaborators and communicators, technologically savvy, and adaptable.

According to Philippine National Research Center for Teacher Quality (2016) cited by Rubio and Saenz (2023) The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) or Developmental National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (d-NCBTS) define what constitutes teacher quality through a set of standards that specify what teachers must be able to know, do, and value in order to provide quality education. Through distinct domains, strands, and indicators that provide measures of professional learning, competent practice, and effective engagement, it describes the characteristics of K–12 teacher

quality. Thus, the PPST is a crucial tool for shaping the teaching profession in the Philippines by setting clear standards, guiding development, and ultimately, ensuring teachers are equipped to provide their students with the best possible education.

Moreover, Teacher Education Council & DepEd (2017) cited by Rubio and Saenz (2023) stated that The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) defines four career stages: Beginning, Proficient, Highly Proficient, and Distinguished, which represent increasing levels of expertise. Beginning Teachers are those pre-service teachers or interns or teachers in their first two years of teaching in public schools. All career stages have 7 domains namely: Domain 1: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy; Domain 2: Learning Environment; Domain 3: Diversity of Learners; Domain 4: Curriculum and Planning; Domain 5: Assessment and Reporting; Domain 6: Community Linkages and Professional Engagement and Domain 7: Personal Development and Professional Development. The 7 domains collectively include 37 strands that pertain to more specific descriptors of teacher practices.

Investing in high-quality pre-service teachers is crucial for achieving quality education. These aspiring educators, who form the foundation of the profession, must be equipped with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes outlined in the PPST. Only then can they effectively foster competent learners, enhance learning outcomes, and ultimately contribute to the Philippines' progress and development by nurturing well-rounded individuals equipped with 21st-century skills and strong values.

Teacher Education Institutions (TEIs) like the Buenavista Community College plays a critical role in shaping the future of education. Their responsibility lies in equipping aspiring teachers, known as "Beginning Teachers" in the PPST framework, with the qualifications required for entry into the profession. This involves mastering the knowledge, skills, and attitudes outlined in the PPST's 7 domains. Through their off-campus student teaching experiences, these pre-service teachers demonstrate the quality of instruction they received at BCC College of Education, ultimately influencing the next generation of learners.

The foundation of successful teaching lies in the skillful combination of two crucial elements: content knowledge and pedagogy. Pre-service teachers, embarking on their journeys to become educators, need to develop both areas concurrently to ensure effective learning experiences for future students.

Kultsum (2017) cited by Luzon and Cubillas (2022) defined Content Knowledge as the knowledge of the specific topic or the ability to understand the subject matter. Therefore, effective content knowledge combines factual knowledge with the ability to think critically and creatively about the subject matter. It allows teachers to not only present information accurately and clearly but also to encourage students to engage with the material in meaningful ways.

Domain 1 recognizes the importance of teachers' mastery of content knowledge and its interconnectedness within and across curriculum areas, coupled with a sound and critical understanding of the application of theories and principles of teaching and learning. This Domain encompasses teachers' ability to apply developmentally appropriate and meaningful pedagogy grounded on content knowledge and current research. It takes into account teachers' proficiency in Mother Tongue, Filipino and English in the teaching and learning process, as well as needed skills in the use of communication strategies, teaching strategies, and technologies to promote high-quality learning outcomes (Llego et al., 2019).

In a like manner, The National College for School Leadership (2014) cited by Luzon and Cubillas (2022) stipulated that content or subject knowledge is a major element of what is transferred, along with teaching skills. In other words, it is very closely related to pedagogical knowledge. Subject knowledge has a very important role to play because high-quality teaching rests on teachers understanding the

subjects they are teaching, knowing the structure and sequencing of concepts, developing factual knowledge essential to each subject and guiding their pupils into the different ways of knowing that subjects provide: subjects create disciplined ways of knowing (Luzon & Cubillas, 2022 p. 6).

Meanwhile, Kurt (2019) on his study posits Pedagogical Knowledge or (PK) which is a generic form of knowledge that encompasses the purposes, values, and aims of education, and may apply to more specific areas including the understanding of student learning styles, classroom management skills, lesson planning, and assessments. This form of knowledge plays a vital role in the success of education that pre-service institutions as well as the rest of the education sectors have to invest in to achieve a greater return of investment that is “quality education.” With this in mind, teachers then, should commit to high quality professional development targeted to develop their expertise. When they do this, they support their growth as a person and a professional who can expertly lead a student to academic success. Concurrently, they will contribute to the realization of the goals and priorities of the classroom and the school system as a whole (Solis, 2018).

To sum up, the successful combination of content knowledge and pedagogy is the cornerstone of effective teaching. This combination allows teachers to effectively communicate their subject matter expertise, engage students in meaningful learning, and ultimately, support their growth and development.

A well-designed learning environment serves as the foundation for a successful student experience. This explores the critical role that safe, secure, fair, and supportive learning environments play in promoting learner responsibility and achievement. Moreover, effective learning environments act as catalysts for positive student development. Beyond physical safety and security, these environments foster a sense of fairness, support, and psychological well-being, which are essential for motivating students to take ownership of their learning (learner responsibility) and ultimately achieve their full potential.

Domain 2 highlights the role of teachers to provide learning environments that are safe, secure, fair and supportive in order to promote learner responsibility and achievement. This Domain centers on creating an environment that is learning-focused and in which teachers efficiently manage learner behavior in a physical and virtual space. It highlights the need for teachers to utilize a range of resources and provide intellectually challenging and stimulating activities to encourage constructive classroom interactions geared towards the attainment of high standards of learning (Llego et al., 2019).

Evans (2008) cited by Mulang (2021) on his study stated that the learning environment encompasses both physical and social aspects that influence the learning process. This interaction is reciprocal while the environment impacts the learner, the learner can also influence the environment. Factors such as facilities, infrastructure, space, lighting, and noise significantly determine the comfort and appeal of the learning setting, which in turn affects student motivation and the overall learning experience. Thus, understanding the different facets of a learning environment allows educators and individuals to optimize the conditions for effective learning and maximize the outcomes of the learning process.

On similar grounds, on the study of Hu (2020) affirmed that conducive classroom environments enhance students' ability to focus, support optimal learning outcomes, and promote a more enjoyable learning experience. Hence, It highlights the importance of creating comfortable classroom conditions as a foundation for effective learning. It emphasizes the interconnectedness of physical well-being, concentration, learning outcomes, and enjoyment in the learning process.

Furthermore, learning environment is the place where the teaching and learning process occurs. The learning environment can affect the success of a learning process. The learning environment is

inanimate objects around the learning place, but the people who are in that place also include the learning environment (Mulang, 2021 p. 87)

From this point, therefore, we can say that a well-designed learning environment goes beyond just providing a space for learning. It actively contributes to and enhances the overall success of a student's educational experience by providing the necessary physical, pedagogical, and psychological support for effective learning and personal growth.

Diverse and responsive learning environments places the spotlight on teachers' crucial role in creating inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of all students. It emphasizes the importance of teachers' knowledge, understanding, and respect for the unique characteristics and experiences each learner brings to the classroom. These diverse backgrounds and perspectives serve as valuable inputs for teachers to design effective and responsive learning opportunities that reach every individual student.

Domain 3 emphasizes the central role of teachers in establishing learning environments that are responsive to learner diversity. This Domain underscores the importance of teachers' knowledge and understanding of, as well as respect for, learners' diverse characteristics and experiences as inputs to the planning and design of learning opportunities. It encourages the celebration of diversity in the classrooms and the need for teaching practices that are differentiated to encourage all learners to be successful citizens in a changing local and global environment (Llego et al., 2019).

On the study of Yin and Chai (2020) they asserted that every human being is unique. We are all born with unique strengths and weaknesses, born into a unique family in a specific time space within a particular sociocultural context. We interact with the world and others and we develop our own unique understandings of them. Regardless of the unique qualities each individual possesses, everyone needs to learn and develop. In any well-developed region, the recognition of diversity in learners' characteristics and the common need for all learners to develop their potential to the fullest undergirds the missions, policies, and practices of education entities. Thus, this stresses the importance of acknowledging that students are not uniform. They come from varied backgrounds, possess unique learning styles, talents, needs, and experiences.

In the same way, Bhogayata and Jadeja (2023) on their study revealed that the teachers had to accommodate the diversity in their concurrent pedagogic and students had to develop new learning styles. The teachers have shown agreement on most of the hypothesis mentioned in the questionnaire; however it was found that catering the students' diversity in the class room is the function of the interpersonal skills, academic experience and ability to communicate effectively with the diversified learners. The results established that the teachers will have to accommodate the learner's diversity by a continuous up gradation and by embracing the new ways of pedagogical practices.

Moreover, Ramdani et al. (2022) stipulated that identification of the diversity of students is often an important point that teachers rarely consider before the learning is carried out. In fact, by understanding this diversity, teachers can undoubtedly carry out adaptive learning and assessments that are suitable for the conditions of student. Thus, the statement advocates for a shift away from a "one size fits all" mentality in education. By understanding the diversity of their students, teachers can create more equitable and effective learning environments where everyone has the opportunity to succeed.

To sum up, it paints a picture of a dynamic classroom where teachers are not just content providers, but responsive architects of the learning experience. It positions student diversity as an asset to

be leveraged and emphasizes the importance of teachers who are knowledgeable, understanding, and proactive in creating inclusive environments where everyone can succeed.

Curriculum and planning explore the vital relationship between teachers and the curriculum framework. It focuses on teachers' engagement with the curriculum, encompassing both national and local frameworks. Delving into their ability to transform curriculum content into engaging learning experiences that consider students' needs and effective teaching principles. It emphasizes the importance of using professional knowledge to individually or collaboratively plan and design well-structured and sequenced lessons that effectively guide student learning.

Domain 4 addresses teachers' knowledge of and interaction with the national and local curriculum requirements. This Domain encompasses their ability to translate curriculum content into learning activities that are relevant to learners and based on the principles of effective teaching and learning. It expects teachers to apply their professional knowledge to plan and design, individually or in collaboration with colleagues, well-structured and sequenced lessons. These lesson sequences and associated learning programs should be contextually relevant, responsive to learners' needs and incorporate a range of teaching and learning resources. The Domain expects teachers to communicate learning goals to support learner participation, understanding and achievement (Llego et al., 2019).

Rice and Mars (2023) on their study stated that curriculum planning is a vital and potentially daunting task. It first involves carefully thinking through what we need (and want) to teach as well as the best strategies for implementation. Second, it involves creating meaningful assessments that demonstrate student mastery of the content. Planning lessons is a critical component to being an effective educator. These instructional decisions inform and lead to what we call our curriculum. The statement highlights both the significance and the potential difficulties associated with curriculum planning. It acknowledges the crucial role it plays in education while recognizing the challenges educators face in designing effective and engaging learning experiences.

Furthermore, on the study of Nurtanto et al. (2021) asserted that the key to the success of the quality of education is not limited to curriculum changes, but rather the readiness and understanding of teachers in carrying out curriculum content. However, the good curriculum is, if the teacher's mindset is not changed, then the curriculum cannot be meaningful. In addition, the characteristics of teachers as curriculum practitioners are influenced by the length of time teachers are involved in the curriculum and high awareness in improving the quality of learning. Hence, it underscores that while a well-designed curriculum is important, it is ultimately the teachers who make it come alive in the classroom. Their knowledge, skills, and understanding are critical in ensuring that students can effectively learn and engage with the content, leading to a higher quality of education.

According to Egan (2003) cited by Madondo (2020) curriculum refers to the study of any and all educational phenomena that may draw on any external discipline for methodological help and does not allow the methodology to determine inquiry. Of necessity, curriculum should aim at producing knowledge that may have educational value to the beneficiaries. Curriculum can be defined as a set of material resources that teachers use to implement a curriculum.

To conclude, curriculum planning involves more than merely designing outlines on paper. It explores the dynamic connection between teachers and the curriculum frameworks they utilize. Effective curriculum implementation relies on teachers who expertly adapt these frameworks to create engaging, relevant, and inclusive learning experiences for their students.

Assessment and Reporting holds immense significance in the educational landscape. It focuses into the processes and strategies employed by teachers to monitor, evaluate, and document the needs, progress, and achievement of their students. It involves on utilizing a variety of assessment tools to gather relevant data that informs not only individual student learning but also the development and improvement of teaching and learning programs as a whole.

Domain 5 relates to processes associated with a variety of assessment tools and strategies used by teachers in monitoring, evaluating, documenting and reporting learners' needs, progress and achievement. This Domain concerns the use of assessment data in a variety of ways to inform and enhance the teaching and learning process and programs. It concerns teachers providing learners with the necessary feedback about learning outcomes. This feedback informs the reporting cycle and enables teachers to select, organize and use sound assessment processes (Llego et al., 2019).

According to Brown (1990) cited by Aquino and Yambi (2020) on his study assessment refers to a related series of measures used to determine a complex attribute of an individual or group of individuals. This involves gathering and interpreting information about student level of attainment of learning goals. Thus, the statement emphasizes that assessing complex attributes requires a multi-faceted approach. It's not enough to rely on one simple measure. Instead, a combination of different tools and methods that are interrelated is needed to gain a comprehensive understanding of the attribute being assessed. This could involve things like tests, observations, interviews, portfolios, or self-assessments.

In addition, Maison et al. (2020) on their study affirmed that assessment is like a facility in maintaining the quality of students' learning with information about learning development. Therefore, it highlights the important role of assessment in supporting and enhancing learning. By providing valuable information about student progress, assessments act as a tool for educators and students to continuously improve the learning experience and ensure it meets the desired quality standards.

The object of assessment could be students' skills, attitudes, interests, or motivation. Apart from determining the profiles of students' skills, instruments can also nurture students' higher-level thinking skills. An appropriate assessment is capable of encouraging students to engage in high-level thinking abilities. To ensure a valid assessment process, the development of standardized and valid instruments is essential (Bhakti et al., 2024. p.57-58).

From this point, therefore, we can say that assessment and reporting are essential tools for ensuring effective teaching and learning in the educational landscape. They provide valuable insights into student progress, inform decision-making, and ultimately contribute to a more effective and successful educational experience for everyone involved.

Community Linkages and Professional Engagement is a vital domain for educators, emphasizing their role in fostering connections beyond the classroom walls. It recognizes the reciprocal value of establishing school-community partnerships that enrich the learning environment for students and engage the community in the educative process. It underscores teachers' responsibility to identify and embrace opportunities that connect classroom learning to the experiences, interests, and aspirations of the broader school community.

Domain 6 affirms the role of teachers in establishing school-community partnerships aimed at enriching the learning environment, as well as the community's engagement in the educative process. This Domain expects teachers to identify and respond to opportunities that link teaching and learning in the classroom to the experiences, interests and aspirations of the wider school community and other key stakeholders. It concerns the importance of teachers' understanding and fulfilling their obligations in

upholding professional ethics, accountability and transparency to promote professional and harmonious relationships with learners, parents, schools and the wider community (Llego et al., 2019).

In a similar note, Mori (2022) on his study stated that it is operationally defined as service or experiential learning where an educator facilitates interaction and collaboration between learners and community members to identify community challenges while learners formulate and implement plans for their understanding and the community's well-being. CE can also be referred to as civic engagement. Learners become explorers and co-creators rather than ordinary acquirers of Knowledge, Skill, and Attitude (KSA). Educators act as facilitators, ensuring that learners' explanations and creations manifest opportunities to apply the content and skills that are mandated by the curriculum.

On the other hand, Watt and Richardson (2008) cited by Karakis (2021) on their study stated that professional engagement' refers to the efforts that prospective teachers have decided to put forward when they start to work and their insistence on continuing the profession. Thus, it reflects a deep investment in the teaching profession and a genuine desire to contribute to the success of students and the educational system.

To conclude, "Community Linkages and Professional Engagement" encourages educators to step outside the classroom, build bridges with the community, and leverage these partnerships to create a richer and more impactful learning environment for their students.

Personal Growth and Professional Development explores the crucial link between a teacher's personal well-being and professional effectiveness. It highlights the importance of uplifting the teaching profession through individual qualities, fostering a culture of self-reflection and continuous learning, and ultimately, fostering a lifelong commitment to growth.

Domain 7 focuses on teachers' personal growth and professional development. It accentuates teachers' proper and high personal regard for the profession by maintaining qualities that uphold the dignity of teaching such as caring attitude, respect and integrity. This Domain values personal and professional reflection and learning to improve practice. It recognizes the importance of teachers' assuming responsibility for personal growth and professional development for lifelong learning. (Llego et al., 2019).

Sancar et al. (2021) on their study affirmed that teachers' professional development (PD) is crucial to improving student outcomes. Because it involves a multidimensional structure and changes across a teacher's professional life. In consequence, it acknowledges that comprehensive and sustained professional development is essential for equipping teachers with the knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to positively impact student learning throughout their careers.

Meanwhile, Gore and Rosser (2020) on their study revealed that professional development provides fresh insights about pedagogy and students, enhances collegiality and collaboration among teachers. Thus, professional development plays a vital role in revitalizing teachers' knowledge and practice while fostering stronger connections and collaboration within the teaching community.

On the contrary, Herman (2020) on his study stipulated that Personal Development offers teachers a better adaptation to the school and social environment requirements, it also decreases the burn-out phenomenon, helps at increasing self-esteem, at consolidation of well-being and also at negative emotions management. The teaching profession is a serious responsibility, which requires skills of emotional self-control, crisis intervention and conflict management, together with the development of an educational relationship with each student. Therefore, personal development empowers teachers to thrive in the

demanding school environment. By enhancing adaptation skills, reducing burnout, fostering well-being, and managing emotions, teachers can approach their professional life with greater resilience, confidence, and effectiveness.

In a like manner, Gyorgy (2018) cited by Herman (2020) postulated that personal development is the foundation of a successful pedagogical act. A self-aware teacher, will have a better understanding, not only of his own person, but also of the children and adolescents, who need so much attention, understanding, modeling and compassion. Simply put, the statement emphasizes that a teacher's commitment to personal development is essential for effective teaching. By being self-aware, understanding their students, and leading by example, teachers can create a positive and impactful learning experience for all.

Objectives

This research aimed to inform strategies for enhancing faculty and pre-service teacher competencies, particularly at Buenavista Community College. The findings could provide valuable insights into how faculty contributions shape pre-service teachers' readiness for both classroom teaching and the LET, ultimately impacting their success as future educators.

METHODS

This study utilized the descriptive correlational research design, which utilizes questionnaires to gather data and information pertinent to the study. According to Bhat (2023), descriptive correlational research is a type of research design that tries to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. It includes collecting and analyzing data on at least two variables to see if there is a link between them. In selecting the respondents of the study, the researchers employed total enumeration sampling. It involves studying the entire population that meets certain predefined criteria, without selecting a subset. This method ensures comprehensive data collection and eliminates sampling bias, making it especially suitable for studies where the population size is manageable and the characteristics of interest are uncommon or specific. For instance, in educational research, if a study focuses on all pre-service teachers enrolled in a particular program at a college, employing total enumeration sampling would involve including every such student in the research. Survey questionnaires were distributed to respondents to achieve the study's main objective: determining the teaching effectiveness and its correlation with pre-service teachers' pedagogical competence and internship performance. Furthermore, the total population sampling method enhances the study's validity by including all eligible respondents, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of current conditions and practices in teaching effectiveness and pre-service training. This approach promotes efficiency, reliability, and clarity in analyzing key educational factors.

The questionnaire was composed of two parts namely, the faculty teaching effectiveness and pre-service teachers' pedagogical competence. The first part of the questionnaire measured the level of faculty teaching effectiveness as perceived by the pre-service teachers. The researcher adopted a questionnaire from the existing Faculty Evaluation Instrument (QCE of the NBC 461). The Qualitative Contribution Evaluation (QCE) instrument, as outlined in the National Budget Circular (NBC) No. 461, serves as a standardized tool for assessing faculty performance in Philippine State Universities and Colleges (SUCs). This instrument evaluates faculty across four key domains: Commitment, Knowledge of Subject, Teaching for Independent Learning, and Management of Learning. These domains are integral to faculty

promotion and ranking processes within SUCs. Faculty teaching effectiveness is measured in the following domains such as Commitment, Knowledge of the Subject Matter, Teaching for Independent Learning and Management of Learning, with item indicators in each area. The data on the level of teaching effectiveness were quantified using the score of a 20 items questions with a five-point Likert Scale. The responses to all items will be analyzed using the Average Weighted Mean. The teaching effectiveness level of the faculty was assessed using a 5-point Likert scale. A rating of Outstanding (4.21–5.00) indicates exceptional performance in teaching. A rating of Very Satisfactory (3.41–4.20) demonstrates a high level of competence in teaching. A rating of Satisfactory (2.61–3.40) indicates that the faculty member meets the expected standards. A rating of Fair (1.81–2.60) suggests that there are areas for improvement in teaching practices. A rating of Poor (1.00–1.80) suggests significant concerns in the faculty member's performance. The second part measured the level of pre-service teachers' pedagogical competence as perceived by their cooperating teachers. The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), implemented through DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017, was used to assess pre service teachers. pedagogical competence. specifically focusing on the indicators for 'Beginning Teachers' (Career Stage 1). This aligns the evaluation with the expected competencies of newly qualified teachers. This serves as the current framework for assessing teachers' competence. This framework marks a significant shift from the previously used National Competency-Based Teacher Standards (NCBTS). Pre service teachers. pedagogical competence is measured in the following domains such as: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development with item indicators in each area. To assess the pedagogical competence of pre-service teachers, a five-point Likert scale was utilized. Each response option corresponds to a defined range of mean scores and a corresponding level of competence. A rating of 5 (with a weighted mean range of 4.21 to 5.00) indicates Advanced Competence, signifying a high level of pedagogical skills and knowledge. A rating of 4 (with a weighted mean range of 3.41 to 4.20) indicates Proficient Competence, reflecting a strong foundation in pedagogical principles and teaching practices. A rating of 3 (with a weighted mean range of 2.61 to 3.40) indicates Basic Competence, suggesting that the pre-service teacher possesses adequate pedagogical skills for classroom practice. A rating of 2 (with a weighted mean range of 1.81 to 2.60) indicates Emerging Competence, which implies that there are areas for improvement in pedagogical knowledge and application. A rating of 1 (with a weighted mean range of 1.01 to 1.80) indicates No Competence, suggesting a significant lack of pedagogical understanding and instructional skill. Furthermore, internship performance of pre-service teachers was assessed using the Final Demonstration Rating completed by their cooperating teacher and faculty observer.

This study was conducted in Buenavista Community College is located at Cangawa, Buenavista, Bohol. It is 82.6 kilometers away from Tagbilaran City. It is a public community college belonging to Local Universities and Colleges (LUCs) that offers quality tertiary education that provides students with free tuition fees for various programs and courses. At present, Buenavista Community College offers undergraduate courses in Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT), Bachelor of Hospitality Management (BSHM), Bachelor of Science in Criminal Justice Education (BSCJE), Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED), Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English (BSED English), and Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Math (BSED Math). A total of two hundred eighty-eight (288) pre-service teachers from the three programs were included in the study: eighty (80) from Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED), one hundred seventy-four (174) from Bachelor of Secondary Education major in English (BSED-English), and thirty-four(34) from Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Mathematics (BSED-Math).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following section presents the results of the study on the teaching effectiveness of faculty and its influence on the pedagogical competence and internship performance of pre-service teachers. The findings are initially presented through tabular form to provide a clear and organized summary of the data, highlighting key statistical results and trends. This is followed by a detailed textual presentation that interprets and explains the data in depth, offering insights into the relationships among the variables and their implications for teacher education and training.

Table 1
Level of Teaching Effectiveness of the Faculty as perceived by the Pre-service Teachers
n=288

Domain	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Commitment	3.75	0.49	Effective
Knowledge of the Subject	3.68	0.48	Effective
Teaching for Independent Learning	3.65	0.49	Effective
Management of Learning	3.63	0.51	Effective
Overall Composite Mean	3.68	0.49	Effective

Table 1 presents the level of teaching effectiveness of the faculty as perceived by the respondents, composed of 288 participants. The evaluation is based on four key domains: Commitment, Knowledge of the Subject, Teaching for Independent Learning, and Management of Learning.

The results indicate that all domains received mean scores ranging from 3.63 to 3.75, which fall within the interpretation range of "Effective" on the 5-point Likert scale. Among the four domains, Commitment got the highest mean score ($M = 3.75$, $SD = 0.49$), suggesting that faculty members are perceived to demonstrate a strong sense of dedication, responsibility, and enthusiasm in fulfilling their teaching duties. This includes punctuality, preparedness, and a visible passion for teaching, which contribute to a positive classroom atmosphere and student motivation.

Additionally, the domain Knowledge of the Subject received a mean score of 3.68 ($SD = 0.48$), indicating that the respondents view their instructors as generally well-versed in their respective subject areas. This implies competence in delivering content accurately, clearly, and with depth, which is essential in fostering academic credibility and learner understanding.

Meanwhile, the domains of Teaching for Independent Learning ($M = 3.65$, $SD = 0.49$) and Management of Learning ($M = 3.63$, $SD = 0.51$) were also rated as effective, though they received slightly lower mean scores compared to the other domains. These results indicate that while faculty are generally effective in fostering learner autonomy and managing classroom instruction, there may be areas for further enhancement in these aspects to maximize student-centered learning and instructional efficiency.

Overall, the composite mean score of 3.68 ($SD = 0.49$) confirms that the teaching effectiveness of the faculty, as perceived by the pre-service teachers, is consistently effective across all evaluated dimensions. However, the relatively lower scores in the domains of independent learning and classroom

management suggest opportunities for professional development aimed at further strengthening these areas.

It supports the study of Kporyi (2021), concluded that the pedagogical competence of teachers could help promote deep knowledge, understanding and expectation among students if teacher's pedagogical competencies are effective.

Table 2
Level of Pedagogical Competence of Pre-service Teachers as perceived by the Cooperating Teachers
n=288

Domain	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	3.78	0.70	Proficient Competence
Learning Environment, Diversity of Learners	3.68	0.69	Proficient Competence
Diversity of Learners	3.59	0.68	Proficient Competence
Curriculum and Planning	3.62	0.68	Proficient Competence
Assessment and Reporting	3.59	0.66	Proficient Competence
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	3.60	0.66	Proficient Competence
Personal Growth and Professional Development	3.57	0.68	Proficient Competence
Overall Composite Mean	3.63	0.68	Proficient Competence

Table 2 presents the perceived level of pedagogical competence of pre-service teachers as evaluated by their cooperating teachers, based on a sample size of 288 respondents. The assessment spans seven core domains aligned with recognized standards of teacher competence.

The results show that all domains fall within the interpretation range of "Proficient Competence", with mean scores ranging from 3.57 to 3.78. This indicates that cooperating teachers generally view the pre-service teachers as demonstrating a solid and consistent level of competence across key pedagogical areas, though still with potential for further growth and mastery.

The domain Content Knowledge and Pedagogy yielded the highest mean score ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 0.70$), suggesting that pre-service teachers are perceived to have a strong grasp of the subject matter and the ability to apply appropriate pedagogical strategies. This reflects positively on their preparation to deliver accurate and engaging lessons, select suitable instructional methods, and scaffold learning based on student needs.

The second highest domain, Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners ($M = 3.68$), also indicates competence in creating safe, inclusive, and supportive classrooms that address learners' varied needs. This is essential in diverse educational settings where cultural, cognitive, and emotional differences must be accommodated to foster effective learning.

Other domains such as Curriculum and Planning ($M = 3.62$) and Assessment and Reporting ($M = 3.59$) reflect the pre-service teachers' ability to design lesson plans, align content with learning outcomes, and utilize appropriate assessment tools. Although competent, these areas may benefit from targeted training in differentiated instruction and the use of assessment data to inform instruction.

The domain Community Linkages and Professional Engagement ($M = 3.60$) points to an adequate level of involvement in school-community relations and professional collaboration. Likewise, Personal Growth and Professional Development ($M = 3.57$), the domain with the lowest mean, still reflects a positive but slightly less developed area. This suggests that while pre-service teachers are receptive to

feedback and committed to self-improvement, they may need greater support and guidance in setting professional goals and engaging in reflective practice.

The overall composite mean of 3.63 (SD = 0.68) confirms that pre-service teachers are generally proficient in their pedagogical skills. The relatively moderate standard deviations across domains imply some variability in perceptions, which could be attributed to differences in the pre-service teachers' individual capabilities, mentoring experiences, or the school contexts where they were deployed.

These findings imply that teacher education programs are successful in cultivating a foundational level of pedagogical competence among their students. However, the results also highlight the importance of reinforcing certain areas—particularly professional development, assessment literacy, and engagement with diverse learners—through enhanced mentorship, practice-based learning, and reflective teaching strategies during their practicum.

The results can inform teacher education institutions in refining their curriculum, practicum design, and support systems to better prepare pre-service teachers for the dynamic demands of the teaching profession.

It supports the study of Manigbas et al. (2024) affirmed that pre-service teachers as future teachers should possess a high degree of competency to provide a conducive learning environment to accommodate the changing needs of the students.

Table 3
Internship Performance of the Pre-service Teachers
n=288

Grading Scale	Frequency	Percentage	Descriptor
1.0-1.1	37	12.85	Outstanding
1.2-1.3	88	30.56	Excellent
1.4-1.5	85	29.51	Very Good
1.6-1.7	63	21.87	Good
1.8-1.9	15	5.21	Satisfactory

Table 3 presents the distribution of pre-service teachers' internship performance as assessed through a grading scale from 1.0 (highest) to 1.9 (lowest acceptable performance). The results reflect the final ratings given to 288 pre-service teachers by their cooperating schools and supervisors based on classroom performance, teaching skills, and professional conduct during their internship.

The data reveal that a significant majority of the pre-service teachers performed at high to exemplary levels: 12.85% (n = 37) attained a rating between 1.0–1.1, classified as Outstanding, indicating exceptional teaching performance, mastery of pedagogical competencies, and a high level of professionalism. The largest portion, 30.56% (n = 88), fell within the 1.2–1.3 range, described as Excellent, suggesting they performed significantly above expectations, demonstrating strong content delivery, classroom management, and instructional planning, 29.51% (n = 85) were rated Very Good (1.4–1.5), showing above-average performance, competence in essential teaching tasks, and consistent professionalism. Another 21.87% (n = 63) achieved a rating of Good (1.6–1.7), which reflects satisfactory performance with some areas for growth, such as in-depth content delivery, assessment strategies, or classroom engagement. Only 5.21% (n = 15) received a Satisfactory rating (1.8–1.9), indicating they met the minimum requirements for internship completion but may require further support or mentoring in specific pedagogical domains.

The findings reveal that the overall strength of the teacher education program, with 72.92% of the pre-service teachers receiving ratings within the Outstanding to Very Good range (1.0–1.5). This suggests that the majority of pre-service teachers were well-prepared for the teaching profession, demonstrating not only foundational competence but also the ability to translate pedagogical knowledge into effective classroom practice.

The small percentage of students in the Satisfactory range indicates areas where additional support, remediation, or extended practice teaching may be warranted. It also points to the variability of individual performance, which may be influenced by factors such as the school environment, mentoring quality, or the student-teacher's adaptability.

These results validate the effectiveness of the internship program as a capstone experience in pre-service teacher preparation. However, it also emphasizes the need for continuous improvement in areas such as differentiated instruction, reflective practice, and classroom-based decision-making, particularly for those who did not perform at the expected level.

The table below presents the relationship between the teaching effectiveness of faculty, pre-service teachers' pedagogical competence, and internship performance, based on data gathered from a sample of 288 respondents. This tabular presentation provides a statistical overview of the correlations among the three key variables, offering insight into how faculty effectiveness may influence the competence and field performance of pre-service teachers.

Table 4
Relationship Between the Teaching Effectiveness of Faculty, Pre-Service Teachers' Pedagogical Competence and Internship Performance
 n=288

Variable	df	α	r	p -value	Interpretatio n	Decision
Teaching Effectiveness of the Faculty and Pre-service Teachers' Pedagogical Competence	286	.05	-0.09	.126	Not significant	Do not reject H_0
Teaching Effectiveness of Faculty and Internship Performance of the Pre-service Teachers	286	.05	-0.19	<.001	Significant	Reject H_0
Pre-service Teachers' Pedagogical Competence and Internship Performance	286	.05	0.11	.059	Not significant	Do not reject H_0

Table 4 presents whether relationships exist between the Teaching Effectiveness of Faculty, Pre-Service Teachers' Pedagogical Competence and Internship Performance. In terms of Teaching Effectiveness of the Faculty and Pre-Service Teachers' Pedagogical Competence, the correlation is found to be not significant ($r(286) = -0.09, p = .126$). Thus, the decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. Although a negative correlation is observed, it is weak and statistically insignificant at the 0.05 level. This suggests that, within this sample, the perceived effectiveness of faculty members did not have a measurable or direct influence on how cooperating teachers rated the pedagogical competence of pre-service teachers. This finding may reflect the complex and multifaceted nature of pedagogical development, which could be influenced by other factors such as personal motivation, individual learning styles, peer collaboration, or prior academic preparation.

Upon an extensive review of the existing literature, no prior studies were found that directly support the current finding indicating a non-significant relationship between faculty teaching effectiveness and the pedagogical competence of pre-service teachers. Most existing research tends to emphasize a positive and significant association between effective teaching and student learning outcomes. The absence of supporting studies for this specific finding suggests that this area remains underexplored and highlights the need for further investigation into the complex, multifactorial influences on the development of pedagogical competence among pre-service teachers.

Consequently, in terms of Teaching Effectiveness of the Faculty and Internship Performance of the Pre-Service Teachers, a significant negative correlation is observed ($r(286) = -0.19, p < .001$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. While the relationship is statistically significant, the direction of the correlation is negative, which is unexpected and needs to be looked into more closely. This unexpected result may be attributed to a number of contextual or methodological factors. One possible explanation is that pre-service teachers under highly effective faculty may be held to stricter evaluation standards, which could lead to more critical assessments during internship. Alternatively, this may reflect variability in the alignment between instructional methods used by faculty and the realities encountered during the internship phase. The findings align with the study of Babu and Mendro (2003), as cited by Francisco and Caingcoy (2022), which emphasizes that teachers play a pivotal role in student success. Their knowledge, commitment, and individualized support significantly influence students' academic achievement, social growth, and overall development.

Lastly, in terms of Pre-Service Teachers' Pedagogical Competence and Internship Performance, the correlation is positive but not statistically significant ($r(286) = 0.11, p = .059$). Although nearing significance, the result implies that there is only a weak association between how cooperating teachers assess pedagogical competence and the final internship ratings received by pre-service teachers. This could indicate inconsistencies in how competence is demonstrated across different settings or reflect that internship performance is influenced by broader professional behaviors, such as adaptability, initiative, and interpersonal skills, which may not be fully captured by pedagogical competence assessments alone.

The findings of this analysis suggest that while faculty teaching effectiveness and pedagogical competence are essential components of teacher education, their direct influence on internship performance may not always be linear or straightforward. The only statistically significant relationship observed was a negative correlation between teaching effectiveness and internship performance, which calls for a critical review of how teaching quality is aligned with the expectations and evaluation practices during field experiences.

The findings are consistent with the study of Bauer et al. (2024), which revealed that although both self-perceived competence and pedagogical knowledge improved over time, there was no significant correlation between them. This suggests that how pre-service teachers perceive their competence may not necessarily reflect their actual performance, underscoring the complex factors that influence success during internships.

The results highlight the importance of coherence between college-based instruction and field-based practice, as well as the need for collaborative alignment between faculty and cooperating teachers to ensure that students are not only pedagogically competent but also able to apply their knowledge effectively in real-world classroom settings. Furthermore, the weak correlations suggest that multiple factors influence internship outcomes, such as emotional intelligence, mentorship quality, classroom dynamics, and institutional support systems. Therefore, future studies may benefit from using mixed-method approaches to capture qualitative insights and deeper patterns behind these statistical relationships.

SUMMARY

1. **Teaching Effectiveness of Faculty.** Based on the evaluations of 288 pre-service teachers, faculty members at Buenavista Community College were rated as generally “Effective” across four domains, with a composite mean of 3.68 (SD = 0.49). The highest-rated domain was Commitment (M = 3.75), Knowledge of the Subject (M = 3.68). Teaching for Independent Learning (M = 3.65), and lastly, Management of Learning (M = 3.63), indicating effectiveness with room for improvement. Low standard deviations suggest consistent perceptions of faculty performance.
2. **Pedagogical Competence of Pre-Service Teachers.** Cooperating teachers rated the pedagogical competence of pre-service teachers as “Proficient” with a composite mean of 3.63 (SD = 0.68). The highest-rated domain was Content Knowledge and Pedagogy (M = 3.78), followed by Learning Environment and Diversity of Learners (M = 3.68), and Curriculum and Planning (M = 3.62). The lowest-rated area was Personal Growth and Professional Development (M = 3.57), indicating a need for more support in reflective practices and career development.
3. **Internship Performance of Pre-Service Teachers.** Internship performance was generally strong, with 72.92% of pre-service teachers rated from Outstanding to Very Good. Specifically, 12.85% were rated Outstanding, 30.56% Excellent, 29.51% Very Good, and 21.87% Good. Only 5.21% received a Satisfactory rating, indicating a need for targeted support such as mentoring or additional training for this small group.
4. **Relationship Among Variables.** Correlation analysis showed: A weak, non-significant relationship between faculty teaching effectiveness and pre-service teachers’ pedagogical competence, suggesting other factors influence competence development. A significant but negative relationship between teaching effectiveness and internship performance, possibly due to higher standards or mismatched evaluation criteria. A weak, nearly significant positive correlation between pedagogical competence and internship performance, indicating that internship success depends on a range of skills beyond pedagogy alone.

These findings highlighted the complexity of teacher preparation and the need for better alignment between instructional practices, competence development, and field performance expectations.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings revealed that faculty members were generally effective, particularly in subject knowledge and commitment, though slightly less so in promoting independent learning and managing the classroom. Pre-service teachers demonstrated proficient pedagogical competence, especially in content knowledge and curriculum planning, but showed weaker development in personal and professional growth. Over 72% performed well in their internships, indicating strong readiness, though some required additional support. Correlation analyses showed no significant link between faculty effectiveness and pedagogical competence, a negative correlation with internship performance, and a weak positive correlation between competence and performance. These highlighted the complexity of teacher preparation and the need for better alignment between instruction, training, and real-world experience to fully equip future educators.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed for key stakeholders:

1. Pre-service teachers may be encouraged to engage in continuous self-improvement by practicing self-reflection, setting clear professional goals, and actively seeking feedback from mentors and cooperating teachers. As part of the action plan, they should maximize their internship experiences by demonstrating professionalism, adaptability, and a strong willingness to learn in real classroom settings. It is recommended that they cultivate a growth mindset, viewing challenges as opportunities to enhance their teaching competence and readiness for the teaching profession.
2. Faculty members are encouraged to enhance their teaching by promoting independent learning, using student-centered strategies, and effectively managing diverse classrooms. They should also strengthen collaboration with cooperating teachers to align classroom instruction with field experiences. Additionally, engaging in professional development and modeling reflective, lifelong learning will support and inspire pre-service teachers.
3. School administrators are encouraged to support comprehensive faculty development focused on innovative teaching, classroom management, and differentiated instruction. Strengthening the internship program through better coordination, aligned evaluation standards, and regular monitoring is also recommended. Additionally, a strong feedback system involving all stakeholders should be established to ensure the teacher education program remains responsive and continuously improves.
4. Future researchers are encouraged to explore additional variables that may influence pedagogical competence and internship performance, such as student motivation, emotional intelligence, and learning styles. Employing mixed-methods approaches, including interviews and classroom observations, is recommended to gain deeper insights into the dynamics of teacher preparation. Expanding the scope of research to include multiple institutions or regional comparisons will allow for broader generalizations and

identification of best practices. Moreover, conducting longitudinal studies that assess the long-term impact of faculty teaching effectiveness and pedagogical training on teaching performance in the field is highly recommended.

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